

E3.6.1 Final design for data management and adaptive learning in 6G

Publication date: 20/06/2024

[6GENABLERS-AI]
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**Programa de Universalización de
Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión – 6G
I+D**

Paquete de Trabajo (PT)	6GENABLERS-SP1-L1-P3
Líder del PT	OPTARE
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Nivel de diseminación	PU
Tipo	RE

Nivel de diseminación	
PU	Publico
PP	Restringido a otros participantes del programa
RE	Restringido a un grupo especificado por el consorcio
CO	Confidencial solo para miembros del consorcio

Tipo	
PR	Prototipo
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SP	Especificación
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OT	Otro

versión	Histórico de versiones del documento			
	Autor	Estado	Fecha	Comentarios
v1.0				

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1 Introduction

This document outlines the architecture and operational components for the final prototype for data management and adaptive learning in 6G. This prototype handles the data life cycle to achieve easy AI data interchange between nodes and allows the ML models to adapt to dynamic environmental changes. It includes all the distributed and handling mechanisms needed to achieve the project's aims.

2 Proposed Architecture for the final design

2.1 Architecture

Figure 1 - Final Design architecture

Component	Purpose	Justification
OTel Collector	To collect, process, and export telemetry (metrics, traces, and logs) from services.	Crucial for aggregating telemetry data in a distributed environment, enabling efficient management of communication overhead and facilitating the analysis of massive and heterogeneous data.
Jaeger (Trace Tracking)	To provide trace tracking to understand the flow of requests through the services of producer, sync, fusion, encoder, decoder, and client.	Essential for data visibility in a distributed environment, allowing the identification of bottlenecks, dependencies between services, and optimizing data flow.
Prometheus (Observability Backend)	To collect and store metrics from services, offering a platform for real-time monitoring and alerts.	Supports data visibility and metric management, crucial for monitoring system performance and health, enabling proactive and reactive adjustments in the infrastructure.
InfluxDB	To serve as a time-series database for storing metrics and events collected by OTel.	Optimized for the storage and querying of time-series data, facilitates the analysis of trends and patterns in data, essential for data-driven decision-making and data lifecycle management.
Feast (Feature Store)	To manage the storage, access, and serving of data features for ML model training and inference.	Key for the reuse of data features and ensuring consistency and quality in model training, supporting transfer learning and efficiency in data lifecycle management.
Apache Airflow	To orchestrate and automate complex workflows and scheduled tasks in data processing and ML operations.	Facilitates the coordination of task dependencies and the automation of ETL and ML workflows, improving reproducibility, efficiency, and scalability in data lifecycle management and ML operations.
Grafana	To visualize metrics, logs, and other data collected from various sources in real-time.	Essential for creating interactive and insightful dashboards, aiding in the monitoring and analysis of system health and performance. Enhances data visibility and helps in quickly identifying and diagnosing issues in a user-friendly manner.

2.2 Cloud infrastructure

Figure 2 - Cloud infrastructure

3 Installation of final design

3.1 Installation of cloud infrastructure

Installation steps:

[1] Container runtimes installation (docker)

<https://docs.docker.com/engine/install/ubuntu/>

[2] Microk8s installation.

<https://microk8s.io/docs/getting-started>

IMPORTANT

Enable following addons:

- cert-manager # Cloud native certificate management
- dashboard # The Kubernetes dashboard
- dns # CoreDNS
- ha-cluster # Configure high availability on the current node
- helm3 # Helm 3 - the package manager for Kubernetes
- hostpath-storage # (core) Storage class; allocates storage from host directory

- metrics-server # (core) K8s Metrics Server for API access to service metrics
- registry # (core) Private image registry exposed on localhost:32000

[3] Create a cluster with microk8s

<https://microk8s.io/docs/clustering>

[4] NFS server settings

<https://microk8s.io/docs/how-to-nfs>

3.2 Installation of components

3.2.1 Observability backend

For comprehensive system observability, this architecture integrates Jaeger for trace analysis, alongside Prometheus and InfluxDB for monitoring metrics and managing alerts. This combination offers a complete view of the system's performance and health.

```
kubectl apply -f k8s\observability_backend\observability-backend-deployment.yaml
```

Prometheus:

- ConfigMap: Basic configuration (prometheus.yml).
- Deployment: Deploys Prometheus with one replica.
- Namespace: observability-backend
- Service: Exposes Prometheus on port 9090.

Basic configuration prometheus.yml:

```
global:
  scrape_interval: 15s
  evaluation_interval: 15s
alerting:
  alertmanagers:
    - static_configs:
      - targets:
          # - alertmanager:9093
rule_files:
  # - "first_rules.yml"
  # - "second_rules.yml"
scrape_configs:
  - job_name: "prometheus"
    static_configs:
      - targets: ["localhost:9090"]
```

Grafana:

- Deployment: Deploys Grafana with one replica, configurations, and dashboards.
- Namespace: observability-backend
- Service : Expose Grafana on port 3000.

InfluxDB2:

```
kubectl apply -f k8s\observability_backend\influxDB2.yaml
```

- PersistentVolumeClaim: Creates influxdb-pvc with 50Gi storage using nfs-csi.
- Name: influxdb.
- Namespace: observability-backend
- Container: influxdb:latest on port 8086 with initialization environment variables.
- Volume: Mounts influxdb-pvc to /var/lib/influxdb.
- Service: influxdb in observability-backend, port 8086.

Environment Variables for Initialization:

- DOCKER_INFLUXDB_INIT_USERNAME:"admin"
- DOCKER_INFLUXDB_INIT_PASSWORD: "admin1234"
- DOCKER_INFLUXDB_INIT_ORG: "optare"
- DOCKER_INFLUXDB_INIT_BUCKET: "metrics"
- DOCKER_INFLUXDB_INIT_ADMIN_TOKEN:
"KCbXUjsNG5ko_FVla9vx2d9oS-
WavbGP1I50UZ6xPN1Okzx6FIwZ3Az4GdTjq1B0v0dxbDR8ILS-u-
Uq0Byj8A=="

3.2.2 OTEL Collector:

OpenTelemetry ensure that updated probes integrate effectively with OpenTelemetry using specific adapters that transform and enrich the collected data with relevant metadata, facilitating analysis and correlation.

- Effective Data Integration: The enhanced probes need to integrate seamlessly with OpenTelemetry. This involves using specific adapters that can transform the raw data collected into a format enriched with relevant metadata. This metadata could include detailed context about the operational state of the host or VM, significantly improving the usefulness of the data for deeper analysis and better correlation.
- Metadata Enrichment: Leveraging the capabilities of OpenTelemetry, metadata such as Kubernetes tags or custom tags that describe the workload or service level can be added to the monitoring data. This provides critical insights that enable network operators to trace issues back to specific virtual machines or host environments.

OTel Agents installation for K8s Cloud infrastructure measurement

OpenTelemetry Configuration: Deploy and configure the OpenTelemetry agent on nodes and VMs to enhance monitoring capabilities. This setup should leverage data enrichment with Kubernetes metadata and advanced metrics collection through specialized receivers.

Figure 3 - k8s cluster metrics

Deploy cert-manager

cert-manager is used by OpenTelemetry operator to provision TLS certificates for admission webhooks.

```
kubectl apply -f https://github.com/cert-manager/cert-manager/releases/download/v1.11.0/cert-manager.yaml
```

Deploy OpenTelemetry operator

```
kubectl apply -f https://github.com/open-telemetry/opentelemetry-operator/releases/download/v0.88.0/opentelemetry-operator.yaml
```

Deploy K8s cluster metrics collector

```
kubectl apply -f k8s\opentelemetry-cloud-measurement\cloud-measurement\collector-k8s-cluster-metrics.yaml
```

3.2.3 ETL

ETL is the mechanism in charge of synchronizing the observability backend (time-series data base) with the offline database (warehouse), which serves as the data source for our feature store platform. This process will be executed through the Apache Airflow workflow orchestration, establishing connections to the time-series and PostgreSQL databases.

Figure 4 - ETL

Customized Airflow Image

We need to create an Apache Airflow image that includes the dependencies we will need to run our DAGs. Below is the customized image with the dependencies `influxdb-client` and `psycopg2-binary`:

```
# Extend from the official Airflow image
FROM apache/airflow:2.8.4

# Switch to root user to install dependencies
USER root

# Install the necessary dependencies
RUN pip install --no-cache-dir influxdb-client psycopg2-binary

# Switch back to the airflow user
USER airflow
```

In our use case, `microK8s` provides with a local images repository. We build the new image, tag it, and push it to the `MicroK8s` registry:

```
docker build -t my-airflow-custom-image:latest .
docker tag my-airflow-custom-image:latest localhost:32000/my-
airflow-custom-image:latest
docker push localhost:32000/my-airflow-custom-image:latest
```

To check that everything went well, run the following query:

```
curl http://localhost:32000/v2/_catalog
```

Expected output:

```
{"repositories":["my-airflow-custom-image"]}
```

Download the Helm repository

```
microk8s helm3 repo add apache-airflow https://airflow.apache.org
microk8s helm3 repo update
microk8s helm3 search repo airflow
```

Apache Airflow Installation

Install the original helm and make a copy of the values file. This will be used to apply custom configurations for our use case.

```
microk8s helm3 upgrade --install airflow apache-airflow/airflow --
namespace airflow --debug
microk8s helm3 show values apache-airflow/airflow > values.yaml
```

Update values.yaml:

[1] Custom image build previously

```
images:
  airflow:
    repository: my-airflow-custom-image
    tag: latest
    pullPolicy: IfNotPresent
```

[2] Set execution, CI/CD Git repo and logs persistence

```
#executor configuration
executor: "KubernetesExecutor"
#gitSync configuration
gitSync:
  enabled: true
  repo: <https://github.com/.....git> # change repository url!
  branch: main
  rev: HEAD
  ref: main
  depth: 1
```

```
maxFailures: 5
subPath: "test/dag" # example !
#logs configuration
logs:
  persistence:
    enabled: true
```

IMPORTANT Please, find value.yaml example in: k8s\ETL\values.yaml

Apply updates

```
microk8s helm3 upgrade airflow apache-airflow/airflow --namespace
airflow --debug --values values.yaml
microk8s helm3 ls -A
```

IMPORTANT If the installation fails, please uninstall and reinstall apache airflow with (-values values.yaml)

Finally create a service if you need to expose airflow-ii:

```
kubectl apply -f k8s\ETL\svc-airflow-webserver.yaml -n airflow
```

The ETL processes will be defined through Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAG) created to specify the tasks of data extraction, optional transformation, and loading, as well as their execution frequency. The extraction task collects the necessary data from observability backend, and the transformation processes these data as needed before the loading task inserts them into offline store (PostgreSQL). Once active, the DAG runs automatically as scheduled, using the Airflow interface to monitor progress and resolve issues. Finally, continuous adjustments and improvements are made to the process, based on observed performance and business needs, to maintain the efficiency and effectiveness of the system.

Install PostgreSQL database.

```
kubectl apply -f k8s\ETL\postgresql_offline_store .
```

Mounting DAG in a Git Repository

Mounting DAGs with Git-Sync in Apache Airflow, you can find a user guide (<https://www.restack.io/docs/airflow-faq-manage-dags-files-04>) (see step 2 above)

Git push DAG file :

```
k8s\ETL\DAG\test\dag\dag_etl_influxDB_to_PostgreSQL extend.py
```


Figure 5 - DAG file

Open airflow ui and select or press auto-refresh, a seconds later will appear **sync_etl_influxdb_to_postgres_extend**.

Figure 6 - Airflow UI

3.2.4 Feature Store

Feast is an open-source framework for storing and serving features to machine learning models. It aims to facilitate the retrieval of feature data from different sources and to this end provides a unified environment for feature management.

This section guides you on how to deploy the Feast feature store service on Kubernetes infrastructure. You can find the necessary resources in the `Feature_store` folder. Follow the steps below to build a Docker image and deploy the service.

Configure `feature_store.yaml`: Update this file to indicate the PostgreSQL URL and connection credentials.

```
project: feast_client
# By default, the registry is a file (but can be turned into a more
scalable SQL-backed registry)
registry: data/registry.db
# The provider primarily specifies default offline / online stores
& storing the registry in a given cloud
provider: local
online_store:
  type: sqlite
  path: data/online_store.db
entity_key_serialization_version: 2
offline_store:
  type: postgres
  host: <your_url_...>
  port: <your_port_...>
  database: postgres
  db_schema: public
  user: feast
  password: feast
```

Define Features in `feature.py`: Use this example file to define your features (`Feature_store\feature_repo\feature.py`)

```
# Define an entity for the driver. You can think of an entity as a
primary key used to
# fetch features.
driver = Entity(name="metrics_service_extend", join_keys=["deployment"])
driver_stats_source = PostgreSQLSource(
  name="metrics_service",
  query="SELECT * FROM metrics_service_extend",
  timestamp_field="_time",
)
```

```

metrics_features_view = FeatureView(
    # The unique name of this feature view. Two feature views in a single
    # project cannot have the same name
    name="metrics_feature",
    entities=[driver],
    ttl=timedelta(days=1),
    # The list of features defined below act as a schema to both define
    features
    # for both materialization of features into a store, and are used as
    references
    # during retrieval for building a training dataset or serving
    features
    schema=[
        Field(name="k8s_pod_cpu_time", dtype=Float32),
        Field(name="k8s_pod_cpu_utilization", dtype=Float32),
        Field(name="k8s_pod_network_io", dtype=Float32),
        Field(name="container_cpu_time", dtype=Float32),
    ]
)

```

Finally build and deploy feature store service

```

cd Feature_store
docker build -t feature-store:latest .
docker tag feature-store:latest localhost:32000/feature-
store:latest
docker push localhost:32000/feature-store:lates

```

To check that everything went well, run the following query:

```
curl http://localhost:32000/v2/_catalog
```

Expected output:

```
{"repositories":["feature-store", "....."]}
```

Deploy feature-store service

```
kubectl apply -f k8s\Feature_store_deployment\feature-store-
deployment.yaml -n observability-backend
```

Start Feature store services

Before starting to work with the Feature store service, apply the configurations defined in sections 4.1 and 4.2.

- Search pod name:

```
kubectl get po -n observability-backend
```

- Copy pod name (example): feature-store-deployment-db96c5457-gtq7d

```
kubectl exec -it feature-store-deployment-db96c5457-gtq7d
/bin/bash -n observability-backend
cd /usr/src/app/feature_repo
feast apply
```

output:

```
Created entity metrics_service_extend
Created feature view metrics_feature
Created feature service metrics_feature
Created sqlite table feast_client_metrics_feature
```

4 Test Integration

To verify the infrastructure, follow the proposed testbench:

Figure 7 - Integration of the components

IMPORTANT, It is necessary to complete installation described on 1-4 sections.

Deploy dummy service:

```
kubectl apply -f k8s\Integration_&_Test\nginx-deployment.yaml -n
default
```

Jmeter (optional)

Figure 8 - Jmeter UI

Check ETL

Figure 9 - ETL in airflow

Figure 10 - ETL info in airflow

Check postgresSQL (offline store)

Figure 11 - Postgres SQL (offline store)

Verify that samples are collected every 10 minutes.

Figure 12 - Get online features

Figure 13 - Get offline features